

COMPARISON BETWEEN CLINICAL AND REAL-LIFE STUDIES WITH A RETROSPECTIVE BULGARIAN REAL-LIFE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) agents, such as intravitreal aflibercept, are available for the treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration. This manuscript aims to compare the outcomes and adherence between regular application of intravitreal aflibercept (IVT-AFL) in a Bulgarian population with literature data from clinical trials and real-life studies.

Materials and methods: We compared local data with data from landmark clinical trials and real-life studies. The Bulgarian study was a retrospective, non-interventional, real-life study with a two-year follow-up. Frequent injection intervals are considered initial dosing of 3 monthly injections of 2 mg IVT-AFL followed by 2 mg IVT-AFL every 2 months for the first year. The patients who adhered to these intervals were assigned to the frequent treatment group and were included in the comparison.

Results: 312 patients diagnosed with age-related macular degeneration were enrolled in Aflibercept treatment. The mean age was 74.2 ± 8.4 years and 60.9% were females. The patients with frequent treatment were 21.8%. The mean visual acuity at the end of the study improved by 0.16 compared to the beginning (0.28 vs 0.44, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The clinical outcomes are similar compared to published clinical trials and higher compared to real-life studies. In addition, this study finds high rates of non-adherence as reported in other real-life studies.

Keywords: macular degeneration, intravitreal aflibercept, real-life study, Bulgaria, frequent treatment, adherence.

Introduction

Anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) agents, such as intravitreal aflibercept, are available for the treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration (AMD), and the goal of disease management beyond the first year is to maintain or improve functional and anatomical gains while minimizing the burden on patients of clinic visits and injections [1]. Although rapid visual and anatomic improvements could be achieved in the first year of anti-VEGF treatment, regression to baseline after initial gains is not uncommon [1].

Real-life studies often suggest less benefit compared to clinical studies mainly due to strict protocol requirements. However, due to the progressive and irreversible nature of the disease and the education of the patient, this gap could be closed in clinical practice.

This manuscript aims to compare the outcomes and adherence between frequent application of intravitreal aflibercept (IVT-AFL) in a Bulgarian population with literature data from clinical trials and real-life studies.

Materials and methods

Local data was analyzed from patients in Bulgaria. We conducted a retrospective, non-interventional, real-life study which is pending publishing. According to the European Summary of Product Characteristics (SPC), treatment at frequent injection intervals is considered initial dosing of 3 monthly injections of 2 mg IVT-AFL followed by 2 mg IVT-AFL every 2 months for the first year. For the study and comparison with similar studies conducted, we allowed an interval of ± 2 weeks for the first year and ± 4 weeks for the second year of treatment. The patients who adhered to these intervals were assigned to the frequent treatment group. The primary endpoint was visual acuity change during the follow-up.

We compared local data with data from landmark clinical trials and real-life studies (using PubMed search for "intravitreal aflibercept" AND "age-related macular degeneration") for visual acuity change (2-year follow-up if available) and frequent treatment prevalence (number of injections).

Results

The Bulgarian population consists of 312 patients diagnosed with AMD which were enrolled in Aflibercept treatment. The mean age was 74.2 ± 8.4 years and 60.9% were females. The patients with frequent treatment were 21.8%. The mean number of the administered 2-year injections was 11.1 for 2 years and the mean time interval between injections for the study period in new and old patients was significantly different

(2.22 vs. 4.18 months). The mean visual acuity at the end of the study improved by 0.16 compared to the beginning (0.44 vs 0.28, $p < 0.05$) and at the end of the study is significantly different between frequent and non-frequent patients (0.44 vs 0.36, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1 and Table 2 present the comparison of our data with landmark clinical trials and real-life studies, respectively.

Table 1.

Comparison of health outcomes with frequent use of IVT-AFL vs. clinical trials

Characteristic	This study	Clinical trials					
		PERSEUS (LOCF fixed population) [1]	RAINBOW (FAS) [3]	ARIES (early treat-and-extend arm) [3]	ALTAIR [5]	VIEW1 (2 mg monthly) [5]	VIEW2 (2 mg monthly) [5]
Number of injections (2-year interval)	11.1	13.1	10.6 (8-13)	12.0	10.8	12.1 – 12.5	12.2 – 12.4
Visual acuity (baseline)	0.28	55	56.3	66.7 (ETDRS letters)	55.0 (BCVA score)	55.2 (BCVA score)	52.8 (BCVA score)
Mean VA change	0.16	0.8 for previously treated 6.7 for treatment-naive	+4.9 ETDRS letters	+ 4.3 ETDRS letters	+7.6 letters for IVT-AFL-2W group and +6.1 letters for IVT-AFL-4W group	+10.9 (ETDRS BCVA)	+7.6 (ETDRS BCVA)

Abbreviations: BCVA - best-corrected visual acuity; ETDRS – Early Treatment Diabetic Retinopathy Study; LOCF – last observation carried forward; FAS – full analysis set; VA – visual acuity

Table 2.

Comparison of health outcomes with frequent use of IVT-AFL vs. real-life data from other countries

Characteristic	This study	Real-life studies				
		Swiss [6]	OCEAN [7]	PONS (treatment group) [8]	FIGHT RETINAL BLINDNESS STUDY GROUP (Completers group) [9]	Ehlken et al. (adherent group) [10]
Number of injections (2-year interval)	11.1	12.7 (8.3 first year, 5.4 second year)	4.5 (1 year)	2.0	13.6	Not reported
Visual acuity (baseline)	0.44	61.5 (ETDRS letters)	52.0 (ETDRS letters)	0.26 (Snellen acuity)	61.4 (Snellen)	0.514
Mean VA change	0.16	+5.0 (ETDRS letters)	+4.2 (ETDRS letters) (1 year)	-0.07 (Snellen acuity)	+6.0 (ETDRS letters)	-0.008

Abbreviations: ETDRS – Early Treatment Diabetic Retinopathy Study; VA – visual acuity

Discussion

This manuscript compares health outcomes and adherence between frequent application of intravitreal aflibercept in a Bulgarian population with literature data from randomized and real-life studies of patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration in Bulgaria.

The inferiority of real-life clinical outcomes compared with clinical trials in nAMD, defined as a lower mean gain or even loss of VA (4.3-10.9 compared to 4.2-6.0), has been described in several larger studies [11-13] and confirmed in our comparison [1,2-10].

In terms of administration of the injections, this study finds a lower number of applications in two years for frequent (11.1 applications) patients compared to some clinical trials like PERSEUS (13.1 in the frequent group) but similar to others like RAINBOW (8-13 in the frequent group) [1,2]. Other real-life studies also reported high rates of both non-persistence and non-adherence [7,8,10]. The high prevalence of non-frequent treatment in real-world settings is worrying since AMD is a progressive disease and loss of visual acuity is often irreversible. In this line, most patients require lifelong therapy. Thus, patient management in AMD treatment must focus more on maintaining the patient's adherence and persistence [14] and education about the disease and its complications is mandatory.

Conclusion

The clinical outcomes are similar compared to published clinical trials and higher compared to some real-life studies. In addition, this study finds high rates of non-adherence as reported in other real-life studies.

References

- Eter N, Hasanbasic Z, Keramas G, Rech C, Sachs H, Schilling H, Wachtlin J, Wiedemann P, Framme C; PERSEUS Study Group. PERSEUS 24-month analysis: a prospective non-interventional study to assess the effectiveness of intravitreal aflibercept in routine clinical practice in Germany in patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration. *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol* 2021;259(8):2213-2223.
- Weber M, Dominguez M, Coscas F, Faure C, Baillif S, Kodjikian L, Cohen SY. Impact of intravitreal aflibercept dosing regimens in treatment-naïve patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration: 2-year results of RAINBOW. *BMC Ophthalmol* 2020;20(1):206.
- Mitchell P, Holz FG, Hykin P, et al. EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF INTRAVITREAL AFLIBERCEPT USING A TREAT-AND-EXTEND REGIMEN FOR NEOVASCULAR AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION: The ARIES Study: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Retina* 2021;41(9):1911-1920. Erratum in: *Retina*. 2022 Sep 1;42(9):e43.
- Ohji M, Takahashi K, Okada AA, Kobayashi M, Matsuda Y, Terano Y; ALTAIR Investigators. Efficacy and Safety of Intravitreal Aflibercept Treat-and-Extend Regimens in Exudative Age-Related Macular Degeneration: 52- and 96-Week Findings from ALTAIR: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Adv Ther* 2020;37(3):1173-87.
- Heier JS, Brown DM, Chong V, Korobelnik JF, Kaiser PK, Nguyen QD, Kirchhof B, Ho A, Ogura Y, Yancopoulos GD, Stahl N, Vittori R, Berliner AJ, Soo Y, Anderesi M, Groetzbach G, Sommerauer B, Sandbrink R, Simader C, Schmidt-Erfurth U; VIEW 1 and VIEW 2 Study Groups. Intravitreal aflibercept (VEGF trap-eye) in wet age-related macular degeneration. *Ophthalmology* 2012;119(12):2537-48. Erratum in: *Ophthalmology* 2013;120(1):209-10.
- Ebneter A, Michels S, Prunte C, Imesch P, Eilenberger F, Oesch S, Thomet-Hunziker IP, Hatz K. Two-year outcomes of intravitreal aflibercept in a Swiss routine treat and extend regimen for patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration. *Sci Rep* 2020;10(1):20256.
- Gunnemann F, Vögeler J, Schmitz-Valckenberg S, Spital G, Liakopoulos S, Ziemssen F (2017) Influence of OCT examination during ranibizumab treatment of AMD patients in a real-life setting (OCEAN study). Abstract presented at the Annual Meeting of The Association for Research and Vision in Ophthalmology (ARVO), Baltimore Convention Center, Baltimore, MD, 6-11 May 2017.
- Ehlken C, Wilke T, Bauer-Steinhilber U, Agostini HT, Hasanbasic Z, Müller S. Treatment of neovascular age-related macular degeneration patients with vascular endothelial growth factor inhibitors in everyday practice: identification of health care constraints in Germany-the PONS study. *Retina* 2018;38:1134-44.
- Barthelmes D, Nguyen V, Daien V, et al. TWO YEAR OUTCOMES OF "TREAT AND EXTEND" INTRAVITREAL THERAPY USING AFLIBERCEPT PREFERENTIALLY FOR NEOVASCULAR AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION. *Retina* 2018;38(1):20-28.
- Ehlken C, Helms M, Bohringer D, Agostini HT, Stahl A. Association of treatment adherence with real-life VA outcomes in AMD, DME, and BRVO patients. *Clin Ophthalmol* 2018;12:13-20.
- Finger RP, Wiedemann P, Blumhagen F, Pohl K, Holz FG. Treatment patterns, visual acuity and quality-of-life outcomes of the WAVE study – a noninterventional study of ranibizumab treatment for neovascular age-related macular degeneration in Germany. *Acta Ophthalmol*. 2013;91(6):540-546.
- Holz FG, Tadayoni R, Beatty S, et al. Multi-country real-life experience of anti-vascular endothelial growth factor therapy for wet age-related macular degeneration. *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2015;99(2):220-226.
- Sivaprasad S, Hykin P, Chakravarthy U, Lotery A, McKibbin M, Napier J. A retrospective study of the real-life utilization and effectiveness of ranibizumab therapy for neovascular age-related macular degeneration in the UK. *Clin Ophthalmol*. 2016;10:87-96.
- Lanzetta P, Loewenstein A, Vision Academy Steering C. Fundamental principles of an anti-VEGF treatment regimen: optimal application of intravitreal anti-vascular endothelial growth factor therapy of macular diseases. *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol* 2017;255:1259-73.